

2021

ANNUAL REPORT

2022

CONTENTS

Welcome / p.3

Reflections on 2021-2022 / p.4
Executive Board Members / p.6
Executive Director's Report / p.7
Statements and Campaigns / p.8
2021-2022 in Numbers / p.9
Our Network / p.10

2018-2022 Strategy / p.11

Strategic Direction #1:
Innovative Scholarly
Communication / p.12

Strategic Direction #2:
Digital Skills & Services / p.14

Strategic Direction #3:
Research Infrastructure / p.15

International Projects / p.16

Annual Conference / p.19

LIBER Quarterly / p. 20

Accounts / p. 22

2021 2022

Cover:
The Luxembourg Learning Centre (LLC),
University of Luxembourg.
Photographer: Oliver Blake

WELCOME

Dear Reader,

Welcome to LIBER's 2021-2022 Annual Report.

Two years of a global pandemic revealed a fundamental truth: in times of crisis, the support of research libraries takes on even greater importance. With that come even greater challenges. Currently, the rising tensions in Eastern Europe due to the ongoing Russia-Ukraine war pose serious consequences for our community. And yet, despite the negative and volatile nature of these world events, we have seen the collective power of people coming together for the upkeep of our commonly shared values.

In the 70s, European research libraries deemed it necessary to join forces to discuss important topics affecting their institutions, and LIBER was born. Half a century later, we see that such collaboration continues to be fundamental – not only for the upholding and protecting of essential, shared values but also for innovation within libraries.

In fact, our recent survey sent to all LIBER Participants has shown the lasting value of our community. Of those who filled out our survey, 88% stated that LIBER's role of making a positive contribution to the broader research library community is crucial. Added to that, 95% of research libraries deemed LIBER fundamental to ensure library views are represented at a European and global level*. With this and other valuable data captured from our survey, we strive to continue our work and also aim to fill in the gaps by helping research libraries tackle current and upcoming challenges.

Despite the challenges we have faced as a community over the last year, importantly, we also want to take the time to celebrate our achievements. As you will see in the coming pages, LIBER Working Groups, European Projects, Executive Board, and Office have worked tirelessly to produce resources, offer training, share expertise, and elevate the profile of LIBER libraries.

We are pleased to say that our combined efforts in the last year have paid off – we have created and will begin the implementation of our 2023-2027 Strategy and we hope to engage you in this within the upcoming months.

Looking ahead, 2022 marks LIBER's 51st year in existence and in turn, our 51st Annual Conference. This will take place in person at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) in Odense – the birthplace of fairytale writer, Hans Christian Andersen. After two conferences hosted online during the pandemic, we are particularly excited to once again welcome our community of research libraries under one roof to participate in a range of inspiring workshops, discussions, presentations, and social events.

I am pleased we can finally come together again to celebrate, reflect, and plan for future challenges together.

Jeannette Frey
LIBER President

* These stats were recorded in May 2022
based on 63 responses from research libraries.

ABOUT THIS REPORT

This Annual Report documents our activities from June 2021-May 2022.

It clarifies how we support research libraries and provide value to LIBER Participants. The report's structure mirrors that of the 2018-2022 Strategy, with sections for each of the three strategic priorities.

In addition, we reflect on the activities of the Executive Board and Office, our participation in international projects, network growth, upcoming activities and the financial accounts.

OUR MISSION

- Provide an information infrastructure to enable research in LIBER Institutions to be world class;
- Enhance the experience of users in LIBER Institutions, which is enriched by the facilities and services which LIBER can offer;
- Promote and advocate for European libraries in all European and national fora where the voice of LIBER needs to be heard;
- Develop library and information professionals who are innovative and can offer leadership to LIBER and to the national/international library community.

OUR VALUES

- High-quality services for all users of library and information services;
- Intellectual freedom and access to scholarship;
- Collaboration with campus, local, national, European and global partners;
- Stewardship of collections and institutional resources, in the most appropriate format;
- Leadership, innovation and a willingness to embrace opportunities for change;
- Inclusivity, equality of opportunity and fulfilment of potential.

REFLECTIONS ON 2021-2022

Astrid Verheusen, LIBER's Executive Director, reflects on the achievements of the past 12 months from the perspective of the Executive Board and the Office.

Executive Board Report

Annually we report on the main events and achievements from the past reporting period, starting from the date of the previous Meeting of Participants of LIBER.

The roughly two-year period we have just lived through has been one of the most striking in modern world history, with the Covid-19 pandemic devastating the planet, effectively shutting down whole industries, human communities of all types, and even entire countries.

However, before we even begin to consider what LIBER has achieved this past year, we must acknowledge the terrible toll the pandemic has taken on the whole of humanity, and remember the lives lost, and the families and friends devastated by grief. We also recognise that not all countries have been equal in their struggles against Covid-19, which continues to shape society, research libraries, and the way in which we interact with each other.

Added to this, the recent war in Ukraine is greatly affecting research libraries, not only in Eastern Europe, but also across the continent, and we need to continue to find ways to support those individuals and institutions affected.

More and more these events have shown us the crucial need for LIBER as an organisation – to bring research libraries together, helping them tackle the range of challenges they face today and in the future.

Shifting to Physical Participation

In 2021, the ongoing impact of Covid-19 on LIBER's work meant that our activities continued to be focused online.

Specifically, our second-ever, fully online conference in June 2021 was a great success, well-attended, and well-reviewed by Participants. It was digitally co-hosted together with our colleagues from the University of Belgrade Library in Serbia (Univerzitetska biblioteka "Svetozar Marković").

Due to recent changes in regulations concerning Covid-19, within the Netherlands and beyond, we are pleased to say that we are now shifting to in-person events again, albeit with our various webinars and training still presented online to allow us to remain as accessible as possible to a European (and global) audience.

In fact, we are excited to report that we have recently completed our first two in-person events of 2022 – LIBER Architecture Working Group Annual Conference (LIBER LAG) in Luxembourg, and the LIBER Emerging Leaders Programme (Cohort 6) in Lyon, France. We are now preparing for our LIBER 2022 Annual Conference in Denmark. Additionally, we hope to host our long overdue and first-ever Winter Event in Amsterdam in December this year.

Finances

LIBER's finances have inevitably been affected by the Covid pandemic. We have suffered substantial loss of income due to the delivery of our conference free and online in summer 2021, and by the inability to receive income from other events.

Projects

We have continued to be successful in winning new project funding, mostly from the European Commission. Although there were some delays in the implementation of projects and events had to be brought online, most projects are now back on track and the acquisition of new projects continues. LIBER Participants are involved as much as possible in the new and ongoing projects.

LIBER'S VISION FOR RESEARCH LIBRARIES IN 2027

Working Groups

Three new Working Groups launched in 2021 – Educational Resources, Data Science in Libraries (DSLlib), and Innovative Peer Review (due to lack of interest, the latter group has been closed). The **Educational Resources Working Group** aims to support European librarians in their role to provide educational resources, both open and online. The **Data Science in Libraries (DSLlib)** Working Group explores and promotes library engagement in applying data science and analytical methods in libraries, taking into account all kinds of processes and workflows around library collections and metadata, as well as digital infrastructures and service areas.

LIBER Quarterly

A number of long-serving LIBER Quarterly (LQ) Editorial Board members stepped down in 2021. We would like to thank board members, past and present, for all their support in 2021. Read more in the LIBER Quarterly Report within this publication.

Collaborations

Two Memoranda of Understanding (MoU) have been signed for the development, promotion, and facilitation of citizen science-related support services at research libraries: one with **SciStarter**, an online citizen science hub, for research libraries in Europe and North America, and one with the **European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)** for research libraries within Europe.

Executive Board Meetings

The Executive Board met online in June and October 2021, and in February 2022.

COMING TOGETHER FOR CHANGE

MS JEANNETTE FREY
LIBER President
Director Bibliothèque Can-
tonale et Universitaire (BCU)
Lausanne

MS ASTRID VERHEUSEN
LIBER Executive Director

DRS ANJA SMIT
LIBER Secretary-General
University Librarian
at Utrecht University

DR HILDE VAN WIJNGAARDEN
LIBER Finance Committee Chair
Director University Library
Vrije Universiteit
Amsterdam

DR GIANNIS TSAKONAS
Chair of the Innovative Scholarly
Communications Steering
Committee
Director Library & Information
Center, University of Patras

DR BIRGIT SCHMID
Head of Knowledge
Commons, Göttingen State
and University Library

Executive Board Members

MR JULIEN ROCHE
Vice-President
Director of Libraries,
University of Lille

DR LARS BURMAN
Director
Uppsala University
Library

**DR ANDREAS
BRANDTNER MBA MSC**
Library Director
University Library
of Freie Universität Berlin,
Germany

DR HELI KAUTONEN
Library Director
Suomalaisen Kirjallisuuden
Seura – Finnish Literature
Society

CÉCILE SWIATEK
Director
University of Paris Nanterre,
France

DR ADAM SOFRONIJEVIC
Deputy Director
University Library "Svetozar
Marković", University of Belgrade

Executive Board Report Continued

New Team Members

During 2021, two new team members joined: Oliver Blake and Rosie Allison, both as Community Engagement and Communication Officers. In 2022, Andrej Vrcon joined as Head of International Projects. Additionally, over the course of the last year we welcomed three interns: Sasha Lam, Bridget Schuiling, and Joeri Both.

With these new colleagues on board, we are in a strong position to steadily expand LIBER services by organising more events, webinars and training activities tailored to the needs of our community.

Covid-19

The Office has been working from home since the start of the pandemic. For much of 2021, we were running all events, activities and meetings exclusively online.

As of March 2022, the Netherlands has abolished all Covid-19 regulations that were in place and we have been returning to the office.

New Strategy 2023-2027

During the last year, great progress has been made on the next LIBER Strategy 2023-2027. The Strategy is fully complete and will be endorsed during the 2022 LIBER Annual Conference in Odense, Denmark. At the conference, Participants will also have the opportunity to give their input on the pillars of the new strategy, the implementation, and the way forward for our community in light of this.

The LIBER Strategy is of great importance to our network and it is for this reason that we have been involving our Participants as much as we can in the process.

Read more about our new Strategy in the coming months on the [news section](#) of our website.

Office Staff (as of May 2022)

- Astrid Verheusen, Executive Director
- Andrej Vrcon, Head of International Projects
- Athina Papadopoulou, Events and Partnerships Coordinator
- Tatsiana Yankelevich, Training Coordinator
- Rozemarie Knigge, Operations Coordinator
- Elizabeth Joss-Bethlehem, Communication Manager
- Rosie Allison, Community Engagement and Communication Officer
- Oliver Blake, Community Engagement and Communication Officer
- Bridget Schuiling, Intern
- Joeri Both, Intern

Sponsors

Despite the challenges our sponsors faced due to not having an in-person conference during 2021, we are pleased to say that we have been able to secure all sponsors for our upcoming, in-person conference. This affirms our sponsors' commitment to LIBER and our community of research librarians.

Stronger Network Ties

We work together with various partners, ADBU, EBLIDA, ECSA, IFLA, SciStarter, SPARC Europe, COAR, and more. The LIBER Executive Board annually reviews our partners. The most up-to-date list can be found [here](#).

Community of Practice (CoP) for Training Coordinators

We participate in OpenAIRE's Community of Practice (CoP) for Training Coordinators and Managers. The CoP has regular calls on making training FAIR, especially when it comes to training within the EOSC.

Statements and Campaigns

07 April 2022

LIBER Signs **Statement** on the Exemption of Not-for-profit Educational and Scientific Repositories, Digital Archives and Libraries from the Digital Services Act.

1 April 2022

Four **Urgent Recommendations** for Open Access Negotiations with Publishers.

29 March 2022

Proposal for a **Digital Services Act** – Research, Education, and Science as Collateral Damage.

2 March 2022

LIBER Statement on Ukraine.

1 March 2022

LIBER Endorses **cOAlition S Letter** to Publishers.

24 February 2022

LIBER Signs **MoU** with the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA).

3 February 2022

LIBER and SciStarter Sign **Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)**.

24 January 2022

LIBER Signs **Public Statement** on Digital Services Act.

25 November 2021

LIBER Applauds **Ratification of UNESCO** Open Science Recommendations.

19 November 2021

LIBER Signs **International Statement of Solidarity**.

23 September 2021

Official **Launch of Knowledge Rights 21** Project – 21st Century Access to Culture, Learning and Research in Europe.

19 August 2021

LIBER and COAR Join Forces to Strengthen the Role of Repositories in Europe.

1 June 2021

Provisional **Adoption of UNESCO Recommendation** on Open Science.

Other events

We represented LIBER and research libraries at events including:

- **2 February 2022:** Diamond Open Access Workshop
- **10 December 2021:** EOSC Association - Extraordinary General Assembly
- **16 November 2021, 18 January 2022:** Board meetings Knowledge Rights 21 Project
- **10 November 2021:** 12 January 2022: Board meetings ORE project
- **6 December 2021:** 17 January 2022: EOSC Taskforce Research Engagement and Adoption
- **6 December 2021:** 17 January 2022: EOSC Taskforce Research Engagement and Adoption
- **8 November 2021:** 12 November 2021: EOSC Taskforce Research Engagement and Adoption
- **3 November 2021:** European Network Association, General Assembly 2021
- **20-24 September 2021:** Open Science Fair & panels, co-organised by LIBER
- **22 September:** Board meetings ORE project
- **16 June 2021:** Board meetings ORE project
- **16 June 2021:** EOSC Symposium
- **15 June 2021:** Board meeting SSHOC project
- **5 June 2021:** General Assembly reCreating Europe project

2021-2022 IN NUMBERS

THE COLLECTIVE POWER OF PEOPLE COMING TOGETHER FOR THE UPKEEP OF OUR COMMONLY SHARED VALUES.

OUR NETWORK

We represent and cooperate with 400+ LIBER Participants – mainly individual research libraries but also consortia, associations and organisations – to ensure that the research library profession can support world-class research.

New Participants

Five institutions joined LIBER between June 2021 and May 2022. Welcome!

- **University of York Library**, United Kingdom
- **NIOD Institute for War, Holocaust and Genocide Studies Library**, The Netherlands
- **Teresa e Alexandre Soares dos Santos Library**, Portugal
- **TSU National Science Library**, Georgia
- **National Scientific Agricultural Library of the National Academy of Agrarian Sciences**, Ukraine

Improving the LIBER Experience

At LIBER, we know that our libraries are at the heart of everything we do. We want to make sure that each Participant gets value out of their LIBER participation, so in the last year, we have increased efforts to communicate our activities more regularly and in different ways.

At the end of 2021 we published the annual [Strategy Update](#) for all Participants, which outlines our achievements during the year.

Since the revamp in 2021 of the [LIBER Insider](#), our monthly newsletter, we are pleased to say that we now reach over 3,500 research library professionals. We also reach thousands of followers with our social media updates on topics such as copyright advocacy and upcoming webinars. We invite all research library professionals to subscribe. In addition to the Insider, our Participants also receive the internal [Quarterly Mailing](#) – geared towards organisational news updates.

At the start of 2022, we launched 'Humans of LIBER', a new monthly campaign which draws upon the pillars of the upcoming LIBER Strategy 2023-2027. We feature real people working at research libraries who make up the LIBER community. We believe that by highlighting our community in a more human manner, we can create genuine connections both within our network as well as outside of it. We hope to see our community inspired by each of these personal stories of working at research libraries. Find our stories via Twitter [#HumansofLIBER](#).

In April 2022, we sent out a satisfaction survey to all Participants to hear more about their opinions and how we can improve as an organisation, the results of which will be published in a report on our website. More details will be made available via the [news section](#) on our website.

Humans of LIBER campaign 2022

HILDE VAN WIJNGAARDEN
Director of the University Library, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
[Read interview](#)

STEVEN CLAEYSSENS
Curator of Digital Collections at the KB, the National Library of the Netherlands
[Read interview](#)

MUTALENI NADIMI
Project Manager, Erasmus University Library
[Read interview](#)

PAUL HOFMAN
Manager of Library Services, Research Support and Education at Eindhoven University of Technology
[Read interview](#)

2018-2022 STRATEGY

The five-year period 2018-2022 promises to bring radical changes to the research landscape.

Our Strategy focuses on those developments where a leading role by LIBER will bring the most added value. It is built on a vision of the research landscape, within which research libraries add value by Powering Sustainable Knowledge in the Digital Age. In practical terms, this means working towards a world in which:

- **Open Access** is the predominant form of publishing;
- **Research Data** is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR);
- **Digital Skills** underpin a more open and transparent research life cycle;
- **Research Infrastructure** is participatory, tailored and scaled to the needs of the diverse disciplines;
- **The cultural heritage** of tomorrow is built on today's digital information.

To realise this, LIBER is working together with its network on the themes identified by three (interconnected) strategic directions: Innovative Scholarly Communication, Digital Skills and Services, and Research Infrastructure.

As an organisation, LIBER brings added value and support in the form of the following enablers:

- **Advocacy and communication capacity;**
- **Engagement in international projects;**
- **Policy development;**
- **Leadership capacity building;**
- **Connecting to our international network and partners.**

Our new 2023-2027 Strategy has been created and will be officially endorsed by LIBER Participants at the Meeting of Participants during the upcoming 2022 LIBER Annual Conference in Odense, Denmark. Thereafter, work will begin on the implementation of the new strategy.

INNOVATIVE SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION

We are strengthening and expanding the roles of research libraries in Innovative Scholarly Communications through our **Citizen Science, Copyright & Legal Matters, Open Access and Educational Resources** WORKING GROUPS.

Citizen Science

The **Working Group** was involved in numerous acts of advocacy with webinars, workshops, posters, and talks both online and at various conferences.

The group also released its first section of the '**Citizen Science for Research Libraries – A Guide**' which is titled, 'Citizen Science Skilling for Library Staff, Researchers, and the Public.'

Moreover, the group has been fundamental in LIBER's signing of two MoUs for the development, promotion, and facilitation of citizen science-related support services at research libraries: one with **SciStarter**, an online citizen science hub, for research libraries in Europe and North America, and one with the **European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)** for research libraries within Europe.

Copyright & Legal matters

The **Working Group of Copyright and Legal Matters** concentrated its efforts in the launching of the Knowledge Rights 21 project, funded by the Arcadia Foundation. The project focuses on eBooks, Open Access (LIBER's #zeroembargo campaign and rights retention), the undermining of copyright exceptions by licenses and technologies, and an open flexible norm in Europe (**read more**). The Knowledge Rights 21 project officially started in late September 2021 and LIBER works on this together with Stichting IFLA Foundation, IFLA, and SPARC Europe.

Additionally, the Copyright & Legal Matters Working Group continued lobbying for the interests of openness and supported the Library Futures initiative as well as addressing the European Commission with regard to the library exemptions in the Digital Services Act (DSA). Consequently, the group played a fundamental role in the release of the following statements:

[LIBER Signs International Statement of Solidarity](#)

[LIBER Signs Public Statement on Digital Services Act](#)

[Proposal for a Digital Services Act – Research, Education, and Science as Collateral Damage](#)

[LIBER Signs Statement on the Exemption of Not-for-profit Educational and Scientific Repositories, Digital Archives and Libraries from the Digital Services Act'](#)

In July 2021, the Working Group also ran a webinar titled, '[eBook Licensing in Europe and the Vanishing Library?](#)'

Open Access

This **Working Group** has collaborated with the Copyright and Legal Matters group for the launch of the #zeroembargo campaign in 2021 and has policies in place that promote sustainable Open Access. Over the past year, the group investigated and assessed various business models and facilitated exchange of best practice in licensing negotiation for off-setting.

Over the past year, a representative from the Working Group has taken part in the SCOSS Advisory Group and links the team with the initiative that supports the sustainability of Open Science infrastructures. Many of these, such as DOAB, have direct links with the sustainability of OA content.

Moreover, the Working Group resumed work on the Think. Check. Submit initiative and also released a new publication, the '[Four Urgent Recommendations for Open Access Negotiations with Publishers](#)' which builds upon an earlier publication, '[Five Principles for Negotiations with Publishers](#)'.

Moreover, the Open Access Working Group presented at the LIBER 2021 Annual Conference on the topic of [open access books](#).

Educational Resources

The new Working Group on **Educational Resources** has recently been set up and a number of meetings have already taken place.

The group is now starting to plan its activities and the deliverables it wants to produce including the submission of two proposals for workshops during the Winter Event in December. One of these will take place together with the Open Access Working Group on the topic of digital accessibility of research publications and educational assets and aims to highlight the need to make these open for all, including the print-disabled users.

Coming Up

- In the coming months, the **Citizen Science Working Group** is due to release the second section of the '[Citizen Science for Research Libraries – A Guide](#)'.
- The **Copyright & Legal Matters Working Group** will be involved in the very first webinar held by the Knowledge Rights 21 Project titled, '[The Empty Library: The Urgency of Solutions to Unsustainable eBook Markets](#)' taking place on the 19th of May 2022.
- The **Educational Resources Working Group** is looking for new members, especially those with expertise in the area of collection management, with a focus on educational material. Make contact with them [here](#).

WE HAVE SEEN THE
COLLECTIVE POWER OF
PEOPLE COMING TOGETHER
FOR THE UPKEEP OF OUR
COMMONLY SHARED VALUES.

We are developing research libraries as hubs for digital skills and services in both physical and virtual environments, and contributing to this goal through our **Digital Scholarship and Digital Cultural Heritage Collections** and **Leadership Programmes WORKING GROUPS**.

Digital Scholarship and Digital Cultural Heritage Collections

During the past year, this **Working Group** rebranded, changing its name from Digital Humanities & Digital Cultural Heritage to Digital Scholarship and Digital Cultural Heritage Collections.

The group also reformed with new members and is exploring how libraries can raise awareness of their work with digital collections to researchers. New areas of activities for the Working Group are: responsible use of digital collections, digital competencies providing expertise, and building relationships with the theme of Digital Impact.

A successful town hall was held on the 15th of November 2021 using the online platform, Gathertown. The group published an **article** in the Art Libraries Journal and LIBER Quarterly, and also improved the best practices fact sheet on 'How to partner with digital scholars'.

Town Hall events

The Digital Scholarship and Digital Cultural Heritage Collections Working Group plans to host two Town Hall events online. Dates are to be confirmed and all details will be made available on the **LIBER Events Calendar**.

Leadership Programmes

The Working Group held a Town Hall event on the Emerging Leadership Programme which was attended by over 40 candidates as a capacity building initiative to support digital activities for researchers.

The group also ran an Alumni Event, held online at the LIBER Annual Conference in 2021, and aimed at previous participants of the Emerging Leadership Group.

Additionally, they ran the first in-person event for LIBER in two years – the **LIBER Emerging Leaders Programme 2022** which was held in Lyon, France in early May.

Coming Up

The **Leadership Programmes Working Group** has the following activities planned:

1) **LIBER Journées 2022**. To take place live in Budapest in May 2022. **The event** will bring together 20-25 library directors to discuss delivering strategic change, as libraries and institutions redefine themselves in continually evolving information and social environments.

2) **Alumni Event**: The Emerging Leaders Alumni will present a workshop during the upcoming LIBER Conference 2022 in Odense, Denmark.

We promote the development of interoperable and scalable infrastructure – which supports sustainable knowledge and is seamlessly linked with institutional services – through our **Architecture, FIM4L, Research Data Management, and Data Science in Libraries WORKING GROUPS**.

Architecture

The group successfully organised the **LIBER Architecture Group Seminar 2022** which took place from the 27th-29th of April 2022 at the Luxembourg Learning Centre of the University of Luxembourg. Over the last year, the Working Group also continued its annual maintenance and updates of the **Library Buildings website**.

FIM4L

Over the past year, this Working Group has conducted the following presentations: IFLA WLIC 2021, UKSG webinar - **'Federated authentication for library resources: can it be trusted?'** and a **lightning talk** at the LIBER Annual Conference 2021. Moreover, the group has been working on a second version of its initial 'Federated Access to Online Resources: Principles & Recommendations for Library Services.'

Research Data Management (RDM)

The Working Group contributed to a **workshop** at the LIBER Annual Conference 2021 on researcher/community engagement and enabling FAIR data. Moreover, the group has established close exchange with RDA (via Interest Groups: Libraries for Research Data, Long Tail, Training) and further exchange via EU projects (e.g. EOSCpilot, RDA Europe, FOSTER).

Data Science In Libraries (DSLlib)

The Data Science in Libraries Working Group (DSLlib) has set up its work space and meets regularly. It has identified three main areas of interest: creating a landscape analysis/overview, team/service building, and funding opportunities, and has shaped up a work plan. Moreover, on the 27th of September 2021 members of the group contributed to a workshop on AI/ML in Libraries, organised by Heli Kautonen and Andrea Gasparini, which gathered feedback and additional input on current strategies and activities in libraries.

Coming Up

- **LIBER's FIM4L Working Group** is in the process of creating a second version of its initial 'Federated Access to Online Resources: Principles & Recommendations for Library Services.' The draft version is now closed for public commentary and the group is currently processing all feedback. This valuable input will help the Working Group create a second, up-to-date version of the principles which libraries can use to give patrons federated access while preserving privacy as far as possible. More details of the publication will be made available within the next few months.
- **The Research Data Management (RDM) Working Group** will further explore opportunities for collaboration with industry initiatives as well as work on an updated version of the **FAIR factsheet**.

INTERNATIONAL PROJECTS

We connect, represent and inform research libraries by participating in strategic and innovative projects.

Project participation has real benefits for our community. As just one example of the advantages of projects, numerous training opportunities and resources are created, from workshops and webinars to reports and white papers. Through our project work in 2021-2022, LIBER co-organised/attended various webinars, workshops and events.

Over the past year we started working on two new projects, Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21) and Citizen-Enhanced Open Science in Southeastern Europe Higher Education Knowledge Hubs (CeOS_SE).

Below you can read about what we have been up to over the past year for each of our projects.

ABOUT

The **Knowledge Rights 21** (KR21) programme is focused on bringing about changes in legislation and practice across Europe that will strengthen the right of all to knowledge. It is built on a conviction that knowledge is essential for education, innovation, cultural participation and that everyone should have the possibility - in particular through libraries, archives and digitally - to access and use it.

OUR ROLE

LIBER represents the interests of European research libraries, their universities and their researchers in several key areas. We lobby policymakers on issues such as Copyright and Open Access. We collaborate with our member libraries on European-funded projects and through events such as our Annual Conference, we create opportunities for library professionals to meet and learn from each other.

VALUE FOR LIBRARIES

Libraries play an important role in any copyright discussion as they seek to improve access to and use of knowledge in a fast changing digital environment. They are uniquely placed to know what elements related to law and licences do not work well causing uncertainties and impeding teaching and research.

Working with public, national, educational, health and research libraries, universities and the wider access to knowledge movement with the aim to build networks and promote copyright reform at the European and national levels. This is done by facilitating fair access to e-books, protecting users' rights and advocating for a legislation scholarly publication.

ABOUT

The CeOS_SE project aims to raise awareness of mainstream Open Science (OS) and Citizen Science (CS) practices in Southeastern European countries specifically in countries that have been seen to perform less well in OS or CS, or where there is limited awareness of

or involvement in major developments related to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

OUR ROLE

LIBER, as the CeOS_SE project coordinator, supports all project activities and is well-versed in OS and CS- being one of the catalysts of open and citizen science in Europe. In fact, OS is at the core of the LIBER Strategy and the organisation is also working towards mainstreaming CS (the LIBER Citizen Science Working Group was established in 2019). Moreover, LIBER is a member of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Association.

VALUE FOR LIBRARIES

LIBER participation in the practice of CeOS empowers libraries in Southeastern European countries to develop as further knowledge hubs by upskilling staff when it comes to connections between OS and CS.

The scientific research process is an important element in establishing new links between science and society. There are several ongoing efforts to create a definition for citizen science or to adopt the best terminology for public engagement in research activities.

ABOUT

INOS aims to modernise the curricula of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) through civic engagement in Open and Citizen Science. INOS offers a means of staying up-to-date on Open and Citizen Science reports, roadmaps, and learning

and training resources for academic and library staff in higher-education institutions. Via the INOS website, users can join an upcoming Open Knowledge event, or an interactive workshop.

OUR ROLE

LIBER participates in activities targeting libraries and supports their active involvement in the discussion of curricula and skills modernisation. LIBER is leading dissemination activities, as well as efforts to engage, raise awareness and foster policy change.

VALUE FOR LIBRARIES

Libraries have already been introduced to INOS via a series of events in previous years. During the last year specifically, libraries had a chance to participate in the following INOS events: **Co-Creating a Roadmap for Capacity Building on Open Science and Citizen Science for Research Libraries** and **Innovative INOS: Bringing Open Knowledge and Innovation to Higher Education**.

Research libraries can also follow the project's work on defining how universities and their libraries can better meet demand for civic engagement, public participation and societal impact, and will benefit from an INOS guide to designing Open and Citizen Science activities in a pedagogically sound way.

NOTABLE RESOURCES

- [Workshop Report – Why Should Universities And Libraries Get Involved In Citizen Science?](#)
- [Workshop Report – Citizen Science: Why Get Involved?](#)
- [Workshop Report – Integrating Citizen Science At Universities: From 'What' To 'How'](#)

ABOUT

reCreating Europe This project rethinks digital copyright law for a culturally diverse, accessible, creative Europe. We will be looking for libraries to share experiences related to digitisation-related issues, including how legal restrictions are dealt with. This will inform guides and best practices. Libraries will also be invited to attend workshops on legal aspects related to digitisation.

OUR ROLE

LIBER participates in GLAM activities focusing on Libraries and Archives and analysing conducts with regard to (i) legal compliance and compliance with policies and standards for Openness; (ii) implementation of technological measures; (iii) adoption of social norms and common practises, particularly if in conflict with formal legal norms and more aligned to Open Knowledge principles; (iv) access to content by people with disabilities. LIBER also leads the work package on Dissemination, Engagement and Outreach, including training activities.

NOTABLE RESOURCES

- [reCreating Europe Training Toolkit](#) – a catalogue of materials produced by the project and its partners that can be used and referenced for your own [training] activities.

VALUE FOR LIBRARIES

Guidelines and the above-mentioned training toolkit will help libraries to get the most out of the current regulatory framework, and will contribute more generally to improving access to culture and enriching cultural diversity. Via an online forum, libraries and other stakeholder groups will be able to access best practices and policy recommendations, and showcase their own work in this area.

Through the project, libraries and other stakeholders can meet, discuss and work with each other, so that everyone benefits by lowering the individual effort required to deal with copyright regulations.

Additionally, various reCreating Europe events have taken place over the last year and may be of interest to research libraries:

Workshops

- [Secondary Publishing Right: Exploring Opportunities and Limitations](#)
- [The State of Exceptions & Limitations: Copyright Flexibilities in the EU & Member States](#)

Webinars

- [Automated Content Moderation: Copyright and Controversial Content](#)
- [The Regulatory Landscape for Copyright Content Moderation: Evaluation and Future Trajectories](#)

ABOUT

SSHOC The SSHOC project has recently come to an end.

The EU-funded SSHOC (Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud) project aimed to encourage secure environments for sharing and using sensitive and confidential data. The project contributed to the European Open Science agenda and the realisation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Over the past years LIBER has helped build the social sciences and humanities portion of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

OUR ROLE

LIBER led the work package on Fostering Communities, Empowering Users and Building Expertise. We developed and coordinated the implementation of strategies to foster communities and build expertise, and directed workshops, webinars, the project's stakeholder forum event and a final conference. We also supported general project communications, worked towards making data findable by being citable, and helped with project governance and sustainability.

VALUE FOR LIBRARIES

Through SSHOC, LIBER libraries were able to participate in training activities and discussions around building the SSHOC and contributing to the EOSC. In 2021, these included workshops at LIBER 2021 Online, as well as webinars and workshops on topics such as:

- [SSHOC'ing drama in the cloud](#); Encoding theatrical text collections for discovery, exploration, and visualisation; the added value of SSHOC/CLARIN services
- [Onboarding Citizen Science and the role of research libraries barriers and accelerators](#)
- [Requesting Crowd Expertise: The SSH Open Marketplace and LIBER](#)
- [SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp](#) (IASSIST pre-conference workshop)
- [SSHOC Workshop: Data Protection in research practice: The GDPR and the ELDAH Consent Form Wizard](#)

NOTABLE RESOURCES

- [Inventory of SSH Citation Practices](#)
- [Inventory of Learning Materials](#)
- [Training Discovery Toolkit for SSH Trainers](#)
- [\(Meta\)data Interoperability Problems report](#)
- [Policy API Tool](#)

SSHOC Final Conference in Brussels, 6th - 7th of April 2022.

Introducing the European Commission's dedicated open access publishing platform:

Open Research Europe

ABOUT

Open Research Europe (ORE) a publishing platform launched by the European Commission. The platform provides all Horizon 2020 beneficiaries and their collaborators with an easy, high-quality venue to publish Horizon 2020 funded research at no cost and in full compliance with the Commission's open access policies.

OUR ROLE

LIBER's role within the project is to spearhead efforts to engage research libraries and other stakeholders who could benefit from the platform. Our activities include the organisation of workshops and webinars to introduce the platform to the relevant stakeholders and provide training. We also contribute to the project's sustainability strategy and ensure that all project news reaches the right audiences within the Open Access landscape in Europe.

Moreover, the ORE project directly relates to LIBER's 2018-2022 Strategy, in particular to our goal to ensure that Open Access is the predominant form of publishing.

VALUE FOR LIBRARIES

The ORE project and the Open Access values this project brings about are at the core of what we at LIBER do. Research libraries can benefit from the platform in a multitude of ways – the primary manner being that researchers and library patrons can utilise the platform for their research and can in turn submit articles in an open manner.

NOTABLE RESOURCES

- [General Flyer about ORE](#)
- [Open Research Europe Survey Outcomes: Perspectives of Libraries on ORE](#)
- [About ORE's Publishing Process](#)

ABOUT

The **European Language Equality (ELE)** project's primary objective is to prepare the ELE Programme in the form of a strategic research, innovation and implementation agenda, as well as a roadmap for achieving full digital language equality in Europe by 2030.

OUR ROLE

LIBER participates by identifying and mapping the landscape of the European Language Equality project in 2020/2021. We do this by assessing the views, needs and vision of European research libraries as far as achieving digital language equality by 2030 is concerned, and by engaging our community on the topic. Further, we will contribute to desk research and collecting feedback for developing a strategic agenda and roadmap. LIBER's role in this project also involves communication, dissemination, exploitation, sustainability and project management activities.

VALUE FOR LIBRARIES

Twenty-four official languages and more than 60 regional and minority languages constitute the fabric of the European Union's linguistic landscape. However, language barriers still hamper communication and the free flow of information across the EU. Multilingualism is a key cultural cornerstone of Europe, and signifies what it means to be and to feel European. Thus, this project aims to bridge the striking imbalance when it comes to support through language technologies, and issue a call to action - highly relevant to research libraries and their patrons within Europe. The project will lay the foundations for a strategic agenda and roadmap for making digital language equality a reality in Europe by 2030.

NOTABLE RESOURCES

- [ELE report by LIBER on the views of language technology users and consumers from the research librarian perspective](#)

MES-CoBraD

ABOUT

Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

OUR ROLE

LIBER participates in activities related to legal and ethical frameworks, landscape analysis and methodology, pilot RDW acquisition, and raising awareness, dissemination and communication. LIBER will lead stakeholder engagement activities and opportunity-based dissemination activities, while its overall role will focus on libraries in the lifecycle of RWD and their role in the creation and uptake of proposed solutions related to data management.

VALUE FOR LIBRARIES

Libraries benefit from involvement as the project brings together a range of experts across various fields (medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication) and combines cutting-edge clinical information and scientific research to improve lives – very useful content for library patrons/researchers in these fields.

NOTABLE RESOURCES

- [Stakeholder Engagement Strategy by LIBER](#)

Libraries and Open Knowledge: from vision to implementation

LET'S COOPERATE & SHARE!

ANNUAL CONFERENCE

Our 50th Annual Conference was hosted online for the second time due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The conference had 1,858 unique participants for 23 online sessions – making it the biggest LIBER conference to date.

The LIBER 2021 Conference marked the second year that we digitally co-hosted an online conference, this time collaborating with the University of Belgrade Library in Serbia (Univerzitetaska biblioteka "Svetozar Marković").

We were able to turn the Covid-19 travel restrictions into an opportunity to pursue our conference online, delivering inspiring speeches and workshops from research library professionals across Europe. We managed to virtually recreate the experience of being on-site at the library while at the same time ensuring the safety and well-being of all our attendees and contributors.

Shifting our conference online and free-of-charge during the last two years allowed us to reach out to previously underrepresented areas of our LIBER network – and those who may have never had the chance to physically travel to one of our conferences.

Our 2021 conference was an overwhelming success with:

- 2 Keynote Speeches
- 2 Panel Discussions
- 6 Workshops
- 6 #HowToRunALibrary Winners
- 8 Posters
- 12 Parallel Sessions
- 1858 Unique Attendees

2022 ANNUAL CONFERENCE

2022 marks a very important milestone, since it will be our first in-person conference in two years due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

The LIBER Annual Conference (<https://liberconference.eu/>) has been established as the hub where research library professionals gather to network, learn and exchange ideas on relevant topics.

This year, we have partnered with our colleagues at the University of Southern Denmark (SDU).

We invite our LIBER Participants to join insightful sessions, network with colleagues, and exercise their voting rights during the Meeting of Participants.

We hope to see you at this year's conference, to be inspired and engage our network.

Future Conferences

2022 – DENMARK / 6 - 8 JULY

Hosted together with the University of Southern Denmark Library (SDU).

2023 – BUDAPEST / 5 - 7 JULY HOSTED TOGETHER

with the Library and Information Centre of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

LIBER QUARTERLY

The Journal of the Association of European Research Libraries

In 2021, LIBER Quarterly (LQ) published Volume 31 with a mix of editorials, case studies and articles. LQ moved to a new platform, openjournals.nl, in July 2021. This move required the restructuring of all historical LQ article DOIs leading to consequences for indexing services and specific issues with Google Scholar which refreshes DOIs only infrequently. Despite these challenges, since the move, article viewing trends have been steadily upward. Because of the platform change, we do not have a full year of usage and performance data. Therefore data presented covers the six-month period for which we have statistics, from July 2021 to December 2021.

Impact

In For the period July–December 2021 there were 2,688 downloads of LQ papers. This represents a strong increase on the previous year, given the number is higher for six months in 2021 than it was for a full year in 2020 (see table below). The new platform, new content strategies and increased use of social media to share publications may be factors in the improved impact of the journal. In addition, some of the developments allowed by the platform change have been very beneficial for increasing views – including the implementation of plugins for connecting DOIs and for seamlessly pushing content to the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ).

Article-level impact metrics	Views	Downloads
2021 (July–December)	6,099	2,688
Average per paper 2020	7,344	1,095

Of papers published between July and December 2021, the most downloaded/viewed article was **Sondervan et al.** Sharing published short academic works in institutional repositories after six months: The implementation of the article 25fa (Taverne Amendment) in the Dutch Copyright Act.

Performance

In 2021 we introduced the content category of ‘guest editorial’. The editorial board suggested this should be a quarterly activity to reflect the journal’s title and allow adequate time to develop ideas for each paper. This new category has proved very successful, generating significant views, allowing LQ to address issues of the moment and attracting a range of new authors, from early-career researchers to more established and high-profile individuals to write for LQ.

Between July and December 2021, LQ’s acceptance rate was 46%, slightly higher than 2020 (43%). In 2021 LQ published 13 papers as follows:

- Editorial (1)
- Guest editorials (2)
- Articles (7)
- Case studies (3)

All papers published in LQ in 2021 received two anonymous peer reviews, as per the LQ policy.

Developments

As noted above, the journal has been operating from the new openjournals.nl platform since July 2021, which is broadly working well. Inevitable technical issues associated with the platform change have mostly been resolved, but there is ongoing work to improve the XML viewer to ensure full metadata is presented on the web views of all papers. Full metadata is available within all PDFs.

LQ has become a member of the Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association, giving access to a global scholarly publishing community. For the first time, the journal has signed up to a similarity checker service to promote and maintain content quality. New policies – for errors, retractions and research data – have been developed, approved and published. In early 2022, a new content category went live on the journal – the LQ ‘practice paper’, to enable a broader content offering and specifically to engage with professional colleagues wishing to formally share their work on a global scholarly Open Access publishing platform.

liberquarterly.eu

Editorial Board

A number of long-serving LQ Editorial Board members stepped down in 2021 and we thank them for their service to LQ over many years: Paul Ayris, Donatella Castelli, Nicolai Constantinescu, Stefan Gradmann, Tibor Koltay, Derek Law, Achim Oßwald, Yasar Tonta and Herbert Van de Sompel.

We welcomed a new member of the LQ Editorial Board – Ann-Sofie Axelsson, Head of the Department of Communication and Learning in Science and Library Director at Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden. The editorial board meets twice yearly – face to face at the LIBER conference in summer and online in winter. The LQ Editorial Board Chair would like to thank board members past and present for all their support in 2021.

LIBER is currently searching for a new Chair of the LQ Editorial Board, prompted by Em. Prof. Mel Collier’s decision to step down in summer 2022 after many successful years. Mel has contributed an enormous amount through his exceptional experience, skills and leadership, steering the journal through its formative years and its subsequent establishment as a highly regarded international Open Access publication. Mel’s colleagues across the LIBER community offer sincere thanks for his significant contribution.

The Editorial Board

- Mel Collier, *Chairman*, KU Leuven, Belgium
- Trudy Turner, *Managing Editor*, University of Kent, United Kingdom
- Ann-Sofie Axelsson, Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden
- Raf Dekeyser, KU Leuven, Belgium
- Göran Hamrin, KTH Royal institute of technology, Sweden
- Heli Kautonen, Finnish Literature Society, Finland
- Angela Repanovici, Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania
- Christian Schlögl, University of Graz, Austria
- Aurélie Terrier, University of Lausanne, Switzerland
- Cristóbal Urbano, University of Barcelona, Spain
- Julian Warner, Queen’s University Belfast, United Kingdom
- Wilhelm Widmark, Stockholm University Library, Sweden

ANNUAL ACCOUNTS 2021

Accounts

LIBER's financial position is sufficient. The financial result for the Foundation for the year ending 31 December 2021 is a profit of €10.638 (2020: a loss of -€82.161). LIBER's capital and liquidity position is such that financial disadvantages can be absorbed.

The Covid-19 crisis has had continued financial consequences for LIBER in 2021. By cancelling all physical events, revenues from registrations and sponsors have decreased. Overall, expenses have also decreased, but at the same time the necessary expenditure for staff was higher than budgeted, and less time than budgeted could be written on projects.

Solvency has raised from 49% to 57% (equity as a percentage of the balance sheet total).

The LIBER Office has supported its Participants' issues wherever possible to provide them with a good basis for coping with the crisis. Services have been transformed from physical to online as much as possible. However, operations at the heart of the affiliated institutions can be affected by this crisis. The financial consequences for the affiliated institutions of LIBER can be dealt with in accordance with the commitments of governments, but this cannot be reported with certainty as of January 2022.

More information about LIBER's finances can be found in the full 2021 Annual Accounts, sent as part of the May Quarterly Mailing.

INCOME

	2021	2020
FROM REGULAR ACTIVITIES		
LIBER Participants	399.325	408.075
Annual Conference	8.500	8.000
Sponsorship	20.000	21.000
Events and activities	-	-
Other revenues	7.410	-
	435.235	437.075
PROJECT FUNDING		
SSHOC	101.758	106.386
INOS	26.258	20.481
reCreating Europe	97.394	49.727
EOSC WS	16.419	7.171
Open Research	26.748	6.205
ELE	23.887	-
MES-CoBraD	65.491	-
Knowledge Rights 21	16.516	-
	374.471	189.970
TOTAL INCOME	809.706	627.045

EXPENDITURE

	2021	2020
Personnel costs	618.083	591.835
Executive Board	-	2.986
Steering Committees	5.896	7.543
Leadership Seminar	2.000	-
LIBER Office	76.818	72.500
LIBER Quarterly	3.711	2.348
Promotion and Representation	8.680	8.919
Operating costs	67.579	20.870
Other expenditure	13.510	2.205
TOTAL EXPENDITURE	796.277	709.206

RESULTS

	2021	2020
FINANCIAL RESULTS	10.638	-82.161
NET RESULT	10.638	-82.161

zenodo